

Politecnico
di Torino

CoARA
Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

CoARA Action Plan

Opinion of the Academic Senate on January 21, 2025,
and approval by the Board of Directors on January 30, 2025

3. Action Plan

This Action Plan of Politecnico di Torino aims to outline strategies and concrete actions to implement the principles and recommendations proposed by CoARA, with the goal of improving the internal research evaluation process. At this stage, as the 2024-2030 Strategic Plan of the current rectoral mandate has not yet been approved, the AP reflects the objectives and actions of the rector's program "*Politointransition*"¹⁶, of the 2021-2024 Gender Equality Plan "*Towards Diversity*"¹⁷, of the 2021-2024 European Charter for Researchers Action Plan, and those developed during preparatory workshops for the upcoming strategic plan held over the summer.

A one-year monitoring process from the date of publication will also prepare for a potential review of the AP to ensure alignment with the objectives and actions of the new University Strategic Plan.

The structure of the AP includes, in its columns:

- The CoARA supporting commitments related to the concrete actions the university intends to implement.
- The actions, highlighting the related fundamental goal-oriented commitments.
- The timeframe within which to implement the proposed actions, considering a five-year horizon from the signing of the Agreement (2022-2027).
- Responsible figures for the actions, typically Vice Rectors for each area and other involved policy figures.
- Administrative and other structures directly involved in implementing the actions.
- Objectives and actions from the rector's program "*Politointransition*" which, following approval of the Strategic Plan (PSA), will become the PSA's strategic objectives.

¹⁶ <https://politointransition.eu/>

¹⁷ https://www.polito.it/sites/default/files/2022-10/GEP%20en_PoliTO_Sito_new.pdf

Supporting CoARA Commitment	Actions	Timeframe	Indicators	Responsibility	Other Vice Rectors involved	Other Structures involved	Polito in transition
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes (individual level)	A.1 Implementation of a more holistic and inclusive evaluation of applications in recruitment and career progression calls.	2025-2027	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Call review Impact analysis 	Vice Rector for Internal Affairs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vice Rector for Human and Economic Resources Vice Rector for PoliTo Strategic Plan Vice Rector for Equal Opportunities, Inclusiveness and Life Quality Vice Rector for Society and Public Engagement, Community, and Rector's Program Implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PEPS Department - People, HR Planning and Development Open Science Study Center GEDI Study Center 	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving the study and work environment Care and development of staff <p>Actions:</p> <p>[19] Revision of the regulations of individual PhD programs in reference to a comprehensive, general regulation of the School;</p> <p>[61] Raising awareness among companies, research institutions, and public administrations about the various skills of PhD students, research fellows, and fixed-term researchers (RTD/A); University;</p> <p>[75] Promotion and recognition of interdisciplinary and international research collaborations, with increased weight in comparative evaluations for faculty;</p> <p>[112] Establishment by the University of a Career Support Unit to actively promote opportunities within academia, research institutions, industry, and public administration, particularly for PhD students, research fellows, and fixed-term researchers, through connections with these institutions.</p> <p>[114] Revision of job announcements to make evaluation criteria flexible, ensuring fair consideration of contributions across all University missions, including service roles within the</p>
	A.2 Review of internal criteria for the evaluation and rewards of PhD students with reference to core commitments 1, 2, and 3	2025		Director Doctoral School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vice Rector for Scientific and Technological Innovation Vice Rector for Education Vice Rector for PoliTo Strategic Plan Vice Rector for Equal Opportunities, Inclusiveness and Life Quality Vice Rector for Society and Public Engagement, Community, and Rector's Program Implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Doctoral School ScuDo PEPS Department - People, HR Planning and Development PoliTO Strategies Study Center GEDI Study Center 	

Supporting CoARA Commitment	Actions	Timeframe	Indicators	Responsibility	Other Vice Rectors involved	Other Structures involved	Polito in transition
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes (structures level)	A.3 Definition of research evaluation criteria for departmental structures	Ongoing		Rector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vice Rector for PoliTo Strategic Plan Vice Rector for Quality Assurance Vice Rector for Human and Economic Resources Vice Rector for Equal Opportunities, Inclusiveness and Life Quality Vice Rector for Society and Public Engagement, Community, and Rector's Program Implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PoliTO Strategies Study Center GEDI Study Center STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division 	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening research facilities Enhancing research support Promoting internationally recognized research <p>Actions:</p> <p>[69]: Encourage the publication of research findings in high-quality journals, both for bibliometric and non-bibliometric research, to increase the international visibility of achieved results.</p> <p>[75]: Encourage and recognize interdisciplinary and international research collaborations, also by enhancing their value in comparative evaluations for faculty.</p> <p>[86]: Promote the dissemination of qualitative-quantitative approaches, scientific methodologies for data analysis and processing, and models for future scenario assessments to public administrations and regional bodies.</p> <p>[107]: Improve the organization of the dashboard for all services related to the University's missions.</p> <p>[108]: Provide access to University's data for analytical and research purposes.</p> <p>[121]: Strengthen PTAB support to Departments based on their specific needs.</p>
	A.4 Review of the University's bibliometric criteria in line with the core commitments of the Agreement.	2025-2027	Summary document of the study results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rector's Representative for the evaluation of research quality Vice Rector for Quality Assurance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PoliTO Strategies Study Center GEDI Study Center STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division WG PoliTO CoARA 		

Supporting COARA Commitment	Actions	Timeframe	Indicators	Responsibility	Other Vice Rectors involved	Other Structures involved	Polito in transition	
7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.	A.5 Presentation of CoARA initiatives and progress, along with the University's Action Plan, to the governance and academic community.	2024-2027 (carried out periodically)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 annual presentation for institutional bodies (PQA, CARTT, Academic Senate) 1 annual workshop annuale open to the academic community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Science Study Center Vice Rector for PoliTo Strategic Plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vice Rector for Human and Economic Resources Vice Rector for Internal Affairs Vice Rector for Quality Assurance 	WG PoliTO CoARA	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening internal training Enhancing participation and sharing <p>Actions:</p> <p>[53] Provide timely and regular information to external audiences on the management and use of facilities and infrastructure, as well as on major achievements.</p> <p>[54] Promote externally the expertise available within departmental and extra-departmental structures, along with the potential of the University's infrastructure.</p> <p>[95] Define the University Communication Plan (encompassing Internal Communication, Institutional Communication, and External Communication to enhance the University's missions) as the foundation for structuring a new communication model.</p> <p>[105] Support University outreach and awareness activities to foster reflection with a science-based approach and engage society, including through the activities of Polito's Centers for Social Impact, Theseus, and Scienza Nuova.</p> <p>[110] Organize events, seminars, and initiatives that promote awareness of diversity and inclusion.</p> <p>[132] Share and discuss with the community, including through University conferences, the issues addressed, and decisions made by the University's governing bodies.</p>	
	A.6 Creation and periodic update of a section on the University's website dedicated to disseminating CoARA initiatives and the implementation of the internal roadmap.	2025-2027 (carried out periodically)	Creation of the dedicated section inside the Polito's website	ARIA Department- University Libraries Division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Science Study Center Vice Rector for PoliTo Communication and Promotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PoliTO Strategies Study Center STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division 		
	A.7 Training on the use of thematic dashboards (particularly the Publications Dashboard) and tools to support evaluation.	2025-2027 (carried out periodically)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PoliTO Strategies Study Center 		STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division	

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7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.	A.8 Preparation of informational materials on the conscious and responsible use of indicators to support evaluation.	2025		GdL PoliTO CoARA	Vice Rector for Internal Affairs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Science Study Center PoliTO Strategies Study Center STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division ARIA Department- University Libraries Division NUMED - Nucleo MultiMedia Design&Production 	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening internal training Enhancing participation and sharing <p>Actions:</p> <p>[53] Provide timely and regular information to external audiences on the management and use of facilities and infrastructure, as well as on major achievements.</p> <p>[54] Promote externally the expertise available within departmental and extra-departmental structures, along with the potential of the University's infrastructure.</p> <p>[95] Define the University Communication Plan (encompassing Internal Communication, Institutional Communication, and External Communication to enhance the University's missions) as the foundation for structuring a new communication model.</p> <p>[105] Support University outreach and awareness activities to foster reflection with a science-based approach and engage society, including through the activities of Polito's Centers for Social Impact, Theseus, and Scienza Nuova.</p> <p>[110] Organize events, seminars, and initiatives that promote awareness of diversity and inclusion.</p> <p>[132] Share and discuss with the community, including through University conferences, the issues addressed and decisions made by the University's governing bodies.</p>
	A.9 Actions aimed at increasing the use of the University's IRIS repository (publications and datasets)	2025-2027 (as necessary)		ARIA Department - University Libraries Division		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Science Study Center PoliTO WG on Open Access Open Access Commission 	
	A.10 Training activities on best practices in scientific publishing and peer review	2025		ARIA Department - University Libraries Division	Open Science Study Center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Access Commission WG PoliTO CoARA 	

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7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.	A.11 Strengthening training and information activities on research data management according to FAIR principles and promoting Open Science practices.	2025-2027 (carried out periodically)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Open Science Starter Kit" seminars, 2-hour sessions on Open Science and research data management according to FAIR principles. Held twice a year for all researchers. Series of short videos on Open Science topics. Series of podcasts on Open Science topics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ARIA Department - University Libraries Division (Open Science Domain Expert) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Science Study Center 		<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening internal training Enhancing participation and sharing <p>Actions:</p> <p>[53] Provide timely and regular information to external audiences on the management and use of facilities and infrastructure, as well as on major achievements.</p> <p>[54] Promote externally the expertise available within departmental and extra-departmental structures, along with the potential of the University's infrastructure.</p> <p>[95] Define the University Communication Plan (encompassing Internal Communication, Institutional Communication, and External Communication to enhance the University's missions) as the foundation for structuring a new communication model.</p> <p>[105] Support University outreach and awareness activities to foster reflection with a science-based approach and engage society, including through the activities of Polito's Centers for Social Impact, Theseus, and Scienza Nuova.</p> <p>[110] Organize events, seminars, and initiatives that promote awareness of diversity and inclusion.</p> <p>[132] Share and discuss with the community, including through University conferences, the issues addressed, and decisions made by the University's governing bodies.</p>
	A.12 Strengthening support for research staff to encourage, across various disciplines, the adoption of Open Science methodologies and practices throughout the research project lifecycle, including support for research staff's diamond open access publishing initiatives.	2025-2027		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vice Rector for Scientific and Technological Innovation Vice Rector for Society and Public Engagement, Community, and Rector's Program Implementation Vice Rector for PoliTo Communication and Promotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vice Rector for Human and Economic Resources Open Science Study Center 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RIMIN Department- Research, Technology Transfer and Innovation ARIA Department - University Libraries Division STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division 	

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8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.	<p>A.13 Participation in the activities of the National Chapter:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of Task 2.3 "Awareness and Training" • Participation in the activities of Tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and Work Package 3 	Ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two training seminars per year organized by T2.3; material made available as Open Educational Resource (OER). • Contribution to the deliverables of the Tasks/WP. 	Open Science Study Center		WG PoliTO CoARA	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public engagement and increased societal involvement • Building and promoting a recognizable identity for the University • Strengthening participation and sharing • Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions:</p>
	<p>A.14 Participation in the activities of the COARA Working Groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiments in Assessment – Idea generation, co-creation, and piloting. • TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research. 	Ongoing	Contribution to the deliverables of the WG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science Study Center • GEDI Study Center 		WG PoliTO CoARA	<p>[76] Repositioning the University on relational platforms and strengthening institutional dialogue with the Municipality, Region, Ministries, as well as CRUI, ANVUR, and ASN.</p> <p>[78] Monitoring and enhancing the University's participation in European and international University Networks, to build and promote partnerships in international projects and initiatives.</p> <p>[134] Gender impact analysis of the University's decisions and the current mechanisms and regulations governing its operations.</p>
	<p>A.15 Dissemination and exchange of best practices within networks, alliances, and international initiatives (UNITE!, CESAER, Magalhães Network, EUA...)</p>	Ongoing	Co-organization or participation as speakers in at least 1 seminar per year.	WG PoliTO CoARA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vice Rector for International Affairs • Rector's Advisor for relations with European and international university networks and for the UniTe! project. 		

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9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.	A.16 Publication of the Roadmap and its updates.	2024-2027 (carried out periodically)		WG Polito CoARA	Vice Rector for Polito Communication and Promotion		<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening participation and sharing <p>Actions:</p> <p>[53] Providing timely and periodic information to the public about the management and use of facilities and infrastructure, as well as the most significant achievements.</p> <p>[95] Definition of the University Communication Plan (including Internal Communication, Institutional Communication, External Communication for promoting the University's missions), forming the basis for the structure of a new communication model.</p> <p>[105] Supporting the University's outreach and awareness activities to stimulate science-based reflection and societal engagement, including through the activities of Polito Centers for Social Affairs, Theseus, and Scienza Nuova.</p> <p>[131] Sharing and introducing a Charter of Values for the Polytechnic Community.</p> <p>[132] Sharing and discussing with the community, including through University conferences, the issues addressed and the choices made by the University's governing bodies.</p>
	(See also actions A6 and A19)						

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10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.	A.17 Enhancement of the Research Registry with a focus on interoperability and the inclusion and promotion of open science products (datasets, software, etc.).	2025-2027	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of a project within the CoARA Boost framework. • Analysis report of the current architecture and project for necessary updates. 	WG PoliTO CoARA	Vice Rector for Scientific and Technological Innovation		<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening research facilities • Enhancing research support • Promoting internationally recognized research • Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions:</p> <p>[57] International promotion of research results through science communication strategies that reach diverse audiences, tailored to the specific field of reference.</p> <p>[86] Promoting the dissemination of qualitative-quantitative approaches, scientific data analysis and processing methodologies, and models for future scenario assessment to public administrations and regional bodies.</p> <p>[134] Gender impact analysis of the University's decisions and the current mechanisms and regulations governing its operations.</p>
	A.18 Implementation of a monitoring system for publications and Open Access products, as well as Open Science activities (OS Dashboard), also using open databases.	2027		STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division	Open Science Study Center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PoliTO WG on Open Access • Open Access Commission • ARIA Department - University Libraries Division • PoliTO Strategies Study Center 	
	A.19 Preparation of an institutional report on Open Science.	2025 - 2027 annual		Open Science Study Center		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PoliTO WG on Open Access • Open Access Commission • ARIA Department - University Libraries Division • STARQ Area - Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Division • PoliTO Strategies Study Center 	

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